

Recommended citation: Fredriksson, C., & Dwek, M. (2019). A software tool for lifelong learning in engineering education. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 423-432). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656435.

A Software Tool for Lifelong Learning in Engineering Education

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Conference Key Areas: Lifelong learning

Keywords: Distance learning, Adult education, Materials, Teaching,

ABSTRACT

Lifelong learning needs to be part of the solution for closing the skills-gap created by a rapid digital transition. It puts demands on educational tools for this purpose. Realistically, this requires a software platform that can be used remotely and that is relatively self-directed to provide the necessary flexibility for prospective users. Professional development and retraining are relevant examples of fertile areas for e-learning/distance learning in the lifelong perspective.

The CES EduPack software platform was specifically developed to support materials teaching at the Engineering Department of Cambridge University in the UK. It has since evolved into a widely used standard tool for areas of both higher and continued education. It is relevant in this context, since a significant number of engineering jobs for graduated students are concerned with design, manufacturing, maintenance or sales of complex technological products relying on safe high-performance materials.

In this paper, experiences from key academic institutions using this materials education tool are reported. In particular, the Open University of the UK which has a history of using the software in their courses for lifelong learning. There are also two specific examples of the software used in distance learning and professional development at other European Universities. The use of the software in these cases relied on four success-factors:

- Software licensing enabling remote use of the tool
- Extensive support-features for self-directed learning
- Embedded and online learning resources
- A number of advanced textbooks (Ashby) supplying theoretical backgrounds

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1 INTRODUCTION

Lifelong Learning (LLL) has been a European policy priority for more than ten years, and almost 20 years have passed since the European Commission’s Working Paper, “Memorandum on Lifelong Learning”. The European Parliament Resolution of 2008 on “Adult learning: It is never too late to learn” [1] urges member states to promote the acquisition of knowledge and to develop a culture of lifelong learning, designed to make adult education more attractive, more accessible and more effective [2].

When the European Council concluded and issued “A Strategic Framework for European Cooperation in Education and Training” in 2009, lifelong learning was therefore prominently featured [3]. The concept of *Lifelong Learning* was defined as “a continuous process that can last throughout a person’s entire life, from quality early childhood education to post-working age. Moreover, learning also takes place outside formal learning contexts, particularly in the workplace” [2].

There is a decreasing demand for jobs requiring low qualifications leading to an increasing need for higher levels of qualifications in knowledge-based industries [2]. In addition to this, the rapid, so called, *digital transition* in industry urgently requires lifelong learning to help close a widening skills gap. For the majority of Europeans, though, lifelong learning is not a reality; obstacles include limited learning opportunities inadequately tailored to the needs of different target groups, a lack of accessible information and support systems, and *insufficiently flexible learning pathways* [2]. As pointed out by the US Department of Education: “A key enabler of continuous and lifelong learning is technology. Technology gives learners direct access to learning and to the building blocks of their knowledge—organized, indexed, and available 24/7” [4].

All of the above generate a demand for *appropriate educational tools*, which is the topic of this concept paper. Realistically, lifelong learning requires a learning platform to (i) be available remotely (distance learning), and (ii) having enough flexibility (part time, evenings, dual learning/WiL etc) for prospective users. Continuing education and retraining require (iii) ability to support professional development, particularly for engineering skills. The adult learner also relies on tools being (iv) self-directed [5], for sufficient independence, as well as (v) enabling personalised learning experiences.

Fig. 1. Relevant aspects of lifelong learning, affecting requirements on software tools

The CES EduPack software platform (referred to later as *the software*) was specifically developed to support materials teaching at the Engineering department of Cambridge University more than 30 years ago. It has since evolved into a widely used standard tool for areas of higher education and has proven suitable also for lifelong learning (see Fig. 2). Materials teaching is important since a significant number of engineering jobs for graduated students are concerned with design, manufacturing, maintenance or sales of technological products relying on safe, high-performance materials.

Fig. 2. The educational phases in terms of traditional engineering careers and the added feature of lifelong learning, responding to demands of the future work-life

This paper considers CES EduPack, which is part of a family of tools used for materials-related applications both in industry and research (CES Selector and Granta MI) [6]. The links and similarities between the academic and industrial applications of the software ensure that lifelong learners acquire relevant skills when using it as part of their continuing education or professional training. Academic licensing options include the possibility to equip all registered students in a controlled manner with time-limited copies of the software to install on their PC/Laptop. The visual platform for material properties (Ashby Charts), the comprehensive databases with eco- and sustainability properties, manufacturing process data with a built-in cost model and the Eco Audit tool for a lifecycle perspective, lend themselves to collaborative multi-disciplinary project work. For these reasons, it has been suggested that the software would be beneficial for, e.g., Global Engineering in a product development context [7]. It does not, however, rely on internet access.

A prime example of a pioneering provider of lifelong learning using such tools is the *Open University* of the UK (OU). They are one of the largest providers of Higher Education in Europe and the UK's only university dedicated solely to distance learning. In this paper, experiences from educators using the software for lifelong learning are reported. OU, in particular, has a long history of using this and other software in their courses for lifelong learning. There are also two examples of the software being used in professional development and distance education at other European Universities.

2 METHODOLOGY

This paper reports on an exploratory qualitative survey, which represents a first step to assess the use of the software in a lifelong learning setting. It is based on the following questions, answered and elaborated freely by three key educators from academic institutions for higher education that have practised distance learning;

- (i) OU, based at Milton Keynes in the UK with 100% distance operated courses
- (ii) UDIMA Universidad a Distancia de Madrid, Spain, also fully distance-based
- (iii) Department of Materials and Manufacturing at Jönköping University (JU), Sweden.

The responses were requested to be based on: “anonymous student comments and feedback (or stats) you might have specifically about the software”. They were summarised by the authors, in a form that facilitates comparison. There was no specific order in the questions, the answers were free format.

The questions were:

1. What relative level are the participants (beginners, advanced, experienced)?
2. How many were taking the course (per class or module)?
3. Is it a single module or a part of a full program (fully integrated, fully flexible, part time etc)?
4. Are there lectures with demos (live or recorded)?
5. Was the teaching synchronous or asynchronous (scheduled or flexible)?
6. Any group interactions (forums, Q&A, threads etc)?
7. How is support handled (on demand, emails, phone, contact hours etc)?
8. How is the CES EduPack introduced (tutorials, ppt, getting started etc)?
9. Were there specific computer labs scheduled (to learn software functionality, material selection, Eco Audit etc)?
10. Are there assignments based on this software (quiz, hand-ins etc)?
11. How is the software used in examination (if at all)?
12. What was the feedback on the software (useful, difficult, eye-opening etc)?

3 IMPLEMENTATION EXAMPLES OF LLL

The answers to the 12 questions listed in section 2 are collated below. The OU have elaborate responses, whereas UDIMA and JU have shorter answers, summarised in Tables 1-3, in their respective sections. The results are discussed in section 4.

Table 1. Summary of responses from OU

Academic Institution	Open University, based at Milton Keynes in the UK Course link: http://www.open.ac.uk/courses/modules/t271
Education	Module offered to students at OU Stage 2 of their adult studies (equivalent to UK National Level 5), 100% distance.
Students	This is the first engineering module at this stage for around 700 students on both engineering and design qualifications. However, all students on these qualifications have studied introductory engineering (with integrated maths) modules, professional skills modules and either an additional maths module (engineering qualification) or a design module (design qualification) at Stage 1. The module is a core requirement for the BEng & MEng qualifications but may also be studied as an independent unit. CES EduPack has recently been introduced, so the feedback from this initial cohort of students is tentative.
Format	CES EduPack is used in a fully distance learning context, with learning materials developed for print and online use. It is utilised as part of an active learning environment and introduced using the OU online Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) in week 2 of the module. The VLE utilises both full module and tutor-student forums for group discussions. Students are encouraged to download the software in the first week and it is put to use continually throughout the Materials part of the module (approximately 6 weeks duration) and call on it in later parts of the module. The main learning is progressive throughout the first 6 weeks of the module and parallels the students learning of materials, with guidance and activities throughout. The intention is regular exposure in small doses rather than an intensive training programme. Students are encouraged to make use of the tool to obtain materials information for other questions not specifically related to the software. Tutorials, both face-to-face and online formats, allow students to interact and they also use an online collaborative tool for group exercises.
Support	There are no lectures with demonstrations, but individual tutors may incorporate demos into tutorials based on their student's needs. The initial introduction encourages the student to make use of the inbuilt help materials within the software and other resources provided by the software supplier. Additional support is generally provided by phone or email by the student's tutor. Many tutors also use Skype and/or Adobe Connect for online demos.

Table 2. Summary of responses from UDIMA

Academic Institution	UDIMA Universidad a Distancia de Madrid, Spain Course link: https://www.udima.es/en/degree-industrial-organisation-engineering.html#plan-estudios
Education	The modules are in Spanish and 100% distance.
Students	43 students (2018/19) in the second grade of a Degree in Industrial Organisation Engineering. They are beginners in Materials Science
Format	The software is introduced via the embedded Video tutorials and some lectures and video conference. Lectures contain recorded demos. The teaching is both synchronous and asynchronous, but usually students prefer asynchronous. One activity is completely based on the software. The students have to answer a video quiz, answer some questions and submit a report with graphics. Group interaction occurs online via a 'forum of doubts'. The software is not part of the final examination yet.
Support	A teaching assistant answers questions via a virtual laboratory classroom (Moodle LMS). Students receive support in some cases by email or phone.

Table 3. Summary of responses from JU

Academic Institution	Jönköping University, Sweden, Department of Materials and Manufacturing Course link: https://ju.se/mam
Education	Part-time Master's programme (60 ECTS), specialised in casting and given in English. It was developed in close collaboration with the Foundry Industry with intentions to contribute to professional development.
Students	Around 45 students in total with a mixed engineering background but no previous experience using the software.
Format	The software is introduced with a lecture and the embedded 'getting started' resource. The modules are in English and are mostly web-based, for example through video lectures, discussion forums and e-meetings. Meetings on Campus for laboratory work occur once or twice per module. Part-time studies (¼ speed), to enable combining studies with work. Examination is done via a report.
Support	Students get support on demand via emails or phone. Questions can also be handled during on-site Campus lab.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results from the survey are discussed in terms of the five components of LLL (see Fig. 1) and related to specific features in the software considered to support these.

4.1 Distance learning

All of the examples in Tables 1-3 above have been selected based on their explicit use of CES EduPack in a distance learning context. The software is delivered for installation controlled by the University on participants individual computers, enabling some online content, such as the student resources within *Learn* (see Fig. 4), to support independent learning away from a University Campus. The software is backed up by a number of textbooks by Ashby [8-9] and open resources available for any student to acquire the necessary theory.

All educational institutions (OU, JU, UDIMA) have been given access to textbooks as well as dedicated *teaching resources*, including lecture units, exercises, case studies that are being used to various degrees in their respective online learning platforms.

Fig. 4. The software contains both online and offline features and student learning resources to enable independent learning away from Campus.

4.2 Flexibility of use

Since the software itself does not rely on an internet connection to function, it is fully flexible to use whenever and wherever (provided power supply). Projects can be saved and retrieved at convenience. Among the educators surveyed in this paper OU report the most flexible approach while JU reports a fully scheduled, though part time, approach. UDIMA utilises both synchronous and asynchronous components. This shows viability of the software in all flexible contexts.

Extensive visual and clickable information about functionality (see Fig. 5) reduces the need for classroom or lab guidance by teaching assistants. A playlist of sequential video tutorials is available in the online mode, which allows the students to learn functions progressing at their own pace. JU uses scheduled Campus labs to ensure software proficiency whereas OU works with tutors to provide necessary instruction.

Fig. 5. Visual and clickable guidance reduces the need for classroom/lab instruction

4.3 Continuing education/professional development for engineering skills

A number of different engineering areas are covered by the available databases (see below), depending on which edition is licensed. Advanced editions (Level 3) cover Standard (mechanical) Engineering, Aerospace, Polymer and Bioengineering as well as Eco Design and Sustainability (see Fig. 6). These satisfy the needs for a wide range of areas for professional development, not only in traditional materials education. JU has demonstrated that the software can be used as part of a close and direct collaboration with the casting industry at the Master's level to promote professional development. The qualifications that can be obtained from the OU are, of course, also useful for continuing education.

Fig. 6. Relevant databases for professional development in many engineering areas

4.4 Self-directed learning, for sufficient independence

The software has been developed to support self-directed learning, both when it comes to operating the software and when it comes to learning the materials-related topics within courses. In order to understand the function and features of the tool, there is an embedded *Getting Started Guide*. In addition to this, there are short online *Video Tutorials*, containing visual demonstrations organised in sequential playlists. To support the coursework, there are extensive *Science Notes* on demand, and a comprehensive introduction to materials (see Fig. 7) for individual self-study.

Fig. 7. Resources that enable self-directed learning, such as Teach-yourself guides

4.5 Personalised learning experiences

OU represents the use of databases for design while UDIMA utilises the Standard Engineering database for industrial engineering students. JU use the Sustainability database for, e.g., environmental assessments within a manufacturing context. The software is highly versatile, as indicated in section 5.3, above. All the advanced databases contain a comprehensive set of thousands of datasheets that cover the relevant material classes (metal alloys, polymers, ceramics and hybrids/composites) as well as manufacturing processes (joining, shaping and surface treatments). This makes it possible to tailor courses and activities to many specialised areas. As many of the students in our survey are considered beginners, the streamlined, yet comprehensive databases at Level 2 are adequate (see Fig. 8). Thus, the software supports individual learning experiences both in terms of topic and complexity level.

Fig. 8. Property chart at Level 2, showing both biological and engineering materials

There is also a wide range of embedded tools for individual directions in the software: visualisation tools for material properties (Ashby Charts) provide information for overview and selection which is useful for most engineers; the Eco Audit tool for a life-cycle perspective is interesting for green engineering and eco design; the built-in cost model and part cost estimator tool support manufacturing and product development. Students may also want to explore lightweighting projects with composites or structural hybrids using the Synthesizer tool.

4.6 Feedback from students and educators

First, we summarize the available student feedback given anonymously by *The Open University* who is still finalising feedback from the first cohort of students, so there are limited responses to date regarding the software and the module as a whole. The majority of students that have so far responded to questions about the software appear to consider it relatively easy to use. Very few had ever used it prior to this module. The main issue encountered appears to be a lack of a MacOS version. A couple wanted a Linux version. A couple of users encountered issues using work computers, being unable to install the software on to these. Some users wanted an option to have multiple projects/graphs open at the same time, to allow for comparisons of graphs. Many, though, expressed liking the software and the information it contained.

The Jönköping University students have been evaluated two consecutive years, 2018 and 2017 (in brackets) on a module which was heavily based on the Life-cycle tool of the software, Eco Audit. The module was: *Environmental Impact Assessment of Castings - TMGS27*. Various aspects of the course were assessed by students from 1 to 7, the latter being the best, with response rates of around 50%. Although the module was not purely focused on using the software, it would have affected the outcome of the questions. One relevant question in the survey was: *Possibility to achieve the intended learning outcomes (through lectures, laborations, seminars, projects, assignments, literature and other teaching aids)*. This was rated 6.5 (6.17) out of 7 by the participants, indicating a complete absence of discontent.

The question about course material would partly reflect the provided resources and the software: *Opinion about the course material (e.g. course literature, scientific literature, recorded lectures, web quizzes, instructions for laborations)* was rated 6.83 (6.17) out of 7. On the explicit question: *The following aspects of the course were positive*, the answers mentioning the software were: “I like CES EduPack and I think it is very useful in the engineering to analyse or be aware in which phase of the life cycle a product has the highest footprint” (“It was good to learn about program that helps you understand the environmental impact like ECO Audit” (sic)). On the question of *what is your overall opinion of the online learning design of the course?* The two answers that explicitly mentioned the software were: “Good course material and software (CES EduPack)” and “Good choice of use project works and CES software” (see Fig. 9). On the explicit issue: *Room for improvement*, the only comment was: “It was difficult to know how much to write in the assignment regarding CES EduPack”.

What is your overall opinion of the online learning design of the course?

Text answers:

competent teachers including their pedagogy.
good course material and software (CES EduPack)

The course is very professionally made. Very practical and the knowledge is transferred in a very effective way!

Good choice of use project works and CES software. The case study in the course, like examples, create more impression and sensibility.

It's good, but it can be hard to get the time for the online meetings suite with the work.

Nice course! Eye opener for me as a Design Engineer!

Fig. 9. Text answers from one course evaluation survey at JU (n=6 students)

In the case of UDIMA, the Educator summarises the experiences from the software as: “useful, but some students have some difficulties with the language”. The Software offers Spanish and other language versions at Level 2, but some parts are only in English. Furthermore, “According to the students the most useful is the database of materials science and engineering”.

5. CONCEPT CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Summary

The concept under investigation was lifelong learning and how this is supported by the CES EduPack software. Even though the scope was limited, it provided interesting glimpses into what can be explored further. The three cases we have reported, demonstrate that the software can and is used successfully in various forms of lifelong learning. Since the platform is not online-based and current licensing enables academic institutions to distribute time-limited software to participants for the licensed period. The combination of embedded student resources, such as *Getting Started* and *Science Notes*, with online support for learning, such as *Learn* and the *Video Tutorials*, facilitates flexibility and self-directed learning, as evident in these examples.

Success factors that were identified are:

- Software licensing enabling remote use of the tool
- Extensive support for self-sufficiency
- Embedded and online learning resources
- A number of advanced textbooks (Ashby) supplying theoretical backgrounds

5.2 Future work

This work should be seen as the starting point. The use of the software in materials-related lifelong learning context should be studied further in quantitative terms and with more specific questions about functionality and benefits. It would also be interesting to explore lifelong learning from outside of the European perspective.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The Authors are grateful to Donald Edwards and Alec Goodyear from the Open University, UK and to Lucas Castro Martínez, Dean of the Department of Industrial Engineering, Universidad a distancia de Madrid, UDIMA. Finally, thanks to Salem Seifeddine, Toni Bogdanoff and Madelene Zetterlind, all three from the School of Engineering at Jönköping University, Sweden and to Christina Keller of the International Business School at the same University.

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